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RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: WODAJO****FIRST NAME: AYCHEW TAFFETA****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

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List your 6 key concepts with the page number in the text:

1. Academic essay writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 6-12)
2. Some rules of thumb for writing a paper (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 12-14)
3. American Vs. British English (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 25-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 33-39)
5. Style guide (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 40-42)
6. Use of Chicago style (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 44-57)

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WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY**1) INTRODUCTION**

The present response paper aims to offer an overview of the ACA-401/ACA-401D [course pack \(period one\)](#) by providing first the general idea of the six key concepts identified from this reading material under review, and then finally ending with a concise conclusion. The course pack is the fourth edition was revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma in 2021. Writing a good academic essay is an art and science. Teaching an artistic skill is demanding, and yet this course pack provides a student at a post-graduate level with academic and professional paper writing basics.

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The material under review is composed of eight chapters and I am expected to go through it. Fulfilling the expectation of writing my first reaction paper required by the first period of this course. In doing so, I have studied this course material thoroughly, and have critically watched the supplemental videos for the first part of this course. Subsequently, familiarizing myself with the subject at hand prepared me for the academic writing of the EUCLID community. In this response paper, I have applied American spelling and employed Turabian citations and referencing format.

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In order to depict my interaction with this assigned material, I have structured the remainder of this paper as follows. The first section briefly described the concept of academic essay writing. Section two highlights the rules of thumb that are instrumental in academic writing. Section three identified the general categories of difference between Standard American English (SAE) and Standard British English (SBE). The next two sections consecutively introduce how to avoid plagiarism and the style guide that postgraduate students are expected to follow as a student of EUCLID University. Section six emphasizes the use of the Chicago style and its usage. Finally, the last section provides the conclusion.

2) ACADEMIC WRITING

The first chapter of the course pack discussed the concept of the academic essay as 'nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work' (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 7). From the onset, this chapter provides various examples of academic writing including:

Research findings or report on empirical fieldwork which may not or may be published in journals, books, newspapers, or other periodicals (or remain as manuscripts, theses, or dissertations); monograph; conference paper; book or literature review; explication; technical report; translation; students' presentations; as well as undergraduate versions on the above (ibid.).

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I concurred that the essence of this chapter is to highlight the idea that essay writing is a set of processes that are composed of various basic steps. These processes are not rigidly linear (ibid.). As reiterated in the course pack, among other things, academic writing essay 'shares some kind of formal prose register, citations and references to other works, use of stable rhetorical moves to define the project's scope, thereby, positioning it in relevant research, and advance new contributions' (ibid.). The authors of the course pack argued that the core objective of any academic writing is to provide an answer for a proposition and to advance an idea based on evidence for a given state of affairs (ibid.).

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In the rest of this chapter, Cleenewerck and Gulma (2021) went on to illuminate and pinpointed the basic steps of writing an academic essay. The first step identified, according to them is starting the essay. This particular phase by itself encompasses three interrelated steps, namely, they are an early start-up, defining the question and analyzing the task, and drafting an initial plan (ibid.). The second identified step is researching the topic of the proposed theme of the intended essay. In this phase, the expected dual role is researching and reading process to produce a final academically written work. Accordingly, what is expected from this dual role is to 'give the knowledge and evidence to develop a thesis and answer' (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 8). After the culmination of the second step, the next identified step is organizing one's own idea for writing the essay by working out 'how to answer the question and how the essay will be structured' (ibid.). The fourth basic step is writing the first draft of the essay having an overall structure of introduction, body, and conclusion format. In connection to writing the first draft of a given essay, the authors also provide a couple of points regarding the main principle of

composing an essay paragraph and provide tips and guidelines for effective writing skills (ibid., 11). The next three successive steps recognized provide guidance for finalizing standard academic essay writing. Accordingly, the essay provides proper reference, editing, and keeping the logical flow with international and professional standards are essential for any academic writing. The authors pinpointed that identifying the exact format of referencing style of the school/program I subscribed to namely, Doctoral of Counter Terrorism and De-realization (DCTD) and 'consistent usage throughout the paper' (ibid.) that being mandatory criteria for referencing the essay. With regard to editing one's own essay, Cleenewerck and Gulma (2021, 12) advised the students to question themselves to answer the following questions:

- Have I answered the question directly and comprehensively as possible?
- Does the argument make sense? Is it balanced and well-researched?
- Is the evidence relevant to and supportive of my argument?
- Have I used a consistent citation style? Have I referenced all my quotes and paraphrases?
- If there were any special instructions or guidelines for this assignment, have I followed them?
- Have I remained within the set word limit?

In the final analysis of, handing the essay the authors also recommended for prospective students 'to read the guidelines of the course and follow them...[identify], how the lecturer/ tutor would like assignments to be presented and to ensure how the student has complied with the requirement' (ibid).

3) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING A PAPER

This section dwells on the rule or principles that one has to follow for writing a paper. As such only a handful of principles are suggested to govern the writing process. These rules identify the procedure for how one own writing is organized in a given paper. In this regard, the first rule of thumb suggested is the importance of stating the thesis statement at the beginning of the paragraph (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 13). The rule is clear and suggested that one must formulate and state the subject matter of his/her essay. It could be written as a single sentence and depicts the governing idea that a given writer claims (Rosenwasser & Stephen, 2019). I can deduce that; the thesis statement is the crucial component of any piece of academic writing. I also contend that it is a proposition to the question of one's own writing that; he/she is about to address as a final rendition.

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The second rule of thumb is to stay focused on the essential aspect of the theme that a writer is about to compose. This principle adheres to the standards involved in the process of writing an academic paper, focusing on relevant aspects of the subject that a given writer is dealing with and providing a brief account of the state of affairs the writer scrutinizes is essential (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021). Accordingly, this renders a given piece of writing to address the essential point and stay on the course, resolving in the theme one has to

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communicate through writing. Thus, avoiding the needless comprehensive review of the theme and focusing on the specificity of the issue is the rule (ibid.).

The subsequent rule of thumb is avoiding making sweeping generalizations (ibid). This is the caution an aspect a writer must take to eliminate logical fallacy in academic writing. This principle is an important feature of academic writing for producing a good academic essay and is an essential tool for jumping to an unsubstantiated conclusion. Sweeping generalization emanates from inadequate or atypical evidence, insufficient sample, faulty, and biased generalization (Wilson, 2019).

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The fourth suggested rule of thumb is to write clearly. To avoid ambiguity in the essay, a student is expected to endorse the following steps, namely: 'writing short sentences, avoiding page-long paragraphs, and being careful to signal transitions' (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 13). Explicitly, a given writer is recommended to find a mechanism to separate sentences that are longer than, say, five lines; discover a technique to break up a paragraph that is longer than 20 lines; then if the paper is divided into sections, it is important be sure to provide a sentence or two as connecting material (ibid.). In line with this principle, the other related rule of thumb is to refrain from tedious and clumsy writing (ibid.). Applying 'some stylistic variety', circumventing 'long strings of prepositional clauses', and 'try not to repeat the same words' (ibid.) are some of the approaches, one can adhere to realize this rule of thumb.

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The next rule of thumb is to cite evidence in supporting the assertion that a student is going to include in his/her essay. Whenever attributing opinions whose beliefs; a given student is about to criticize, he/she makes sure to include supporting excerpts from a non-fictional text (ibid.). Consequently, this can be done by quoting the passage in which the excerpt was found (ibid.).

The other rule of thumb is to take the views of writers that one has to consult critically. The two strategies were recommended by Cleenewerck & Gulma (2021, 14) for students in order to take a view of a given piece of writing seriously. The strategies that the student has to follow are to "argue against [his/herself]" and make an effort to go "inside" the topic he/she is about to address (ibid.). Finally, one important rule of thumb is that a given student must observe in his essay writing to be original and avoid plagiarizing other writers' work (ibid.).

4) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

Understanding and distinguishing American versus British English is crucial in the academic writing process. This is because the respective academic enterprises follow the conventions of a specific style of English. All students are expected to endorse this style of English when writing their dissertation, research paper or essay. Thus, the most important principle in this regard is that students try to be consistent in their usage of the chosen style in their academic essays. In this course pack, Cleenewerck & Gulma (2021, 25) summarized the 'general categories of difference between standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE) each have their socialistic value'. According to

these writers, some of these categories include those words with different pronunciations, although having the same spelling; words with different spelling, although the same pronunciation (ibid., 26); those words with the same term, different but similar spelling and pronunciation; those words with the same words, but different or additional meanings (ibid.). There are also categories about grammar, syntax, punctuation, and general usage; differences in usage with SBE 'large collective nouns' (ibid.); as well as differences in usage with SBE 'pluralized adjectives' (ibid., 27).

In this course pack, the major variance between SAE and SBE identified are common usage differences (ibid.); the use of some concepts (different terms or expressions) and the use of the same word (differences in style, connotation and frequency) (ibid., 28). Some of the other differences lie with respect to "creativity": spinoffs; combos; referencing of current events and brands' (ibid.); 'Euphemistic references' (ibid., 29); "equality" Vocabulary' (ibid.); and "politically correct" references' (ibid.), etc. The other category of differences is associated with regional variation, identity, and stereotyping (ibid., 30). This includes variations in terminology, particularly "Four-letter words," Obscenities and Implied Obscenities' (ibid.31); 'Differences with Punctuation and Dates' (ibid.); 'Periods, Commas, and Quotation Marks' (ibid.); and 'Punctuation with Business (Formal) vs. Social (Informal) Letters' (ibid., 32).

5) PLAGIARISM

In this course pack, plagiarism is viewed as a state of existence. According to Cleenerwerck & Gulma (2021, 34), plagiarism is defined as 'when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information'. The implied meaning of this definition indicates that a student is cautioned and that he/she does 'not give in to the temptation of copying what someone else has produced...if the student does that, he/she will run the risk of being accused of plagiarism' (Jong 2017, 39). By implication, if students summarize, synthesize, or paraphrase something, they must always give credit to the references from which they have consulted (Greene & Lidinsky, 2018). This is because 'so much of academic writing involves interweaving the ideas of others into one's own argument' (ibid., 229). In doing so, in academic writing students are required 'to use and document sources appropriately, making clear to readers the boundaries between...[their] words and ideas and those of other writers' (ibid.). Thus, the most important question in this regard is how to avoid plagiarism in academic writing.

The obvious solution to the above question has a dual and interrelated answer: namely, 'always cite the sources' (ibid., 230) as well as 'provide a full citation in your bibliography (ibid.). In citing the sources, students are also expected to indicate that they 'are paraphrasing, summarizing, or synthesizing by identifying...[their] source at the outset -acknowledge the source as often as...[they] use it (ibid.). In addition to citing the sources in their essay, students 'must also provide a full citation for every source ...[they] use in the list of sources at the end of ...[their] paper' (ibid.). The fundamental rationale behind why one writer should cite a source is first, 'plagiarism is wrong and unethical' (Cleenerwerck & Gulma (2021, 34); second, it 'is not fair to take someone's work and not give them credit' (ibid.); third, it is also palpable that plagiarism 'is a serious academic

offence that can have serious consequences' (ibid.). In citing a source, the method student used to follow is an in-text citation and writing references at the end of their essay. For applying in-text citations, students can instrumentalize this usage via quotations, and paraphrases (ibid., 36). Moreover, in integrating references, there is also the format students follow in writing a bibliography according to the tradition of their academic enterprise and convention of reference format.

6) STYLE GUIDE

According to Cleenewerck & Gulma (2021, 41); a style guide is conceptualized 'as a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent'. In terms of content, a style guide covers a wide range of topics, from grammar and language usage to the font and height of headings in a work, namely: preferred sentence lengths; manuscript layout; font usage; depth of treatment of a subject; -spelling (UK vs. US for example); readership considerations; use of abbreviations; accepted terminology; the use of symbols; voice preferences (active vs. passive); structure; paragraph numbering and indentation; the use of headings; the use of lists; and trademark or branding considerations (ibid., 41-42).

As I can deduct from the above lists of style guide fundamentals; certainly, it covers the whole lot students need to know to make their essays seem and read exactly like every other work published in that style. Thus, I can say that a 'style guide should be an invaluable tool for any writer' (ibid., 42). A style guide facilitates uniformity, clarity, and ease of communication in the prescribed process of essay writing among students, in many places, and many circumstances within the realm of their respective academic enterprises.

7) CHICAGO STYLE

As the preceding section described the concept of the style guide, this section focuses on knowing which style guide is endorsed by the EUCLID academic community. Chicago style is the specific in-house style of EUCLID as well as it is manual for students' term papers, theses, and dissertations (ibid., 44).

The Chicago style is the widely-used style guide in EUCLID and it has its manual for instrumentalizing this style and practice. This style and usage include content about the specific use of abbreviations; capitalization; compound words; emphasis: italics/quotes; numbers and dates; and quotations (ibid.).

8) CONCLUSION

In this response paper, I have attempted to summarize the essence of the course pack (period 1) that highlights the process of academic writing. The most important issues I emphasize in this reaction paper are academic essay writing, some of the rules of thumb

for writing a paper, American VS. British English, plagiarism, style guide, and the use of Chicago style. Among other things, I explicitly selected these themes to demonstrate my serious interaction with this study material. I believe this interaction is crucial for my learning process of academic writing and an essential entry point for the long journey of my doctoral studies at EUCLID. I concurred that my engagement in this course pack realizes the first stride for pursuing a [Ph.D.](#) in Counterterrorism and Deradicalization.

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In the final analysis, I could say, this first session convinced me that writing good academic essays is indispensable and a good command of advanced English is an essential currency in this regard to convince academically and professionally in the international arena.

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